

Recent advances and trends in the Perovskite-type structures used for solar cells and hydrogen storage

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Abstract: Perovskite-type structures are having unique crystal architecture and chemical composition which make them highly attractive for solar cells and hydrogen storage applications. Hydrogen has been recognized as a clean and renewable energy source for future energy demands. To fully harness the potential of hydrogen energy, storage becomes a pivotal parameter. Researchers' attention has increasingly been captivated by the perovskite materials owing to their advantages of adjustable structures and compositions, coupled with a wide range of raw material sources. This review describes recent studies of the hydrogen storage capacity including (1) a brief introduction to the perovskite structure; (2) a thorough survey of the gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity in perovskite-type hydride; (3) a comprehensive summary of various perovskite-type hydride in hydrogen storage capacity. It provides an insightful perspective on perovskite for hydrogen storage applications and innovation in the development of hydrogen storage for further research and beyond. 13
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1. Introduction

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There is an ongoing enormous demand for new energy sources caused by the rapid global economic development and steady population growth worldwide. Fossil fuels are still the primary source of energy. However, the increased use of fossil fuels has led to several pressing issues, particularly environmental pollution and climate changes [1,2]. Hence, the society is seeking for suitable alternative energy sources such as hydropower, wind, geothermal, tidal, solar thermal, photovoltaics and/or hydrogen [3–5]. The relatively low installation and maintenance costs make the photovoltaic systems a highly attractive source of renewable energy. These systems utilize solar modules, each consist of a large number of solar cells [6,7]. The first solar cells were based on silicon and were developed at Bell Laboratories in 1954 by *Chapin et. al* [8]. Drawback of the silicon cells are the expensive production, rigidity and efficiency limitations at is it getting closer to theoretical limits [9,10]. To overcome these limitations, next-generation materials for solar cells have been extensively studied. Among them perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have attracted significant attention from the community due to their excellent optoelectronic properties such as high absorption coefficients, long charge-carrier diffusion lengths, low exciton binding energies, tuneable bandgaps, and power conversion efficiency (PCE) > 25% [11–17]. Furthermore, PSCs offer significant commercial advantages like low-cost fabrication, flexibility, and low weight, making them promising contenders for the next generation of renewable energy sources [18–20]. 27
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It is noteworthy that perovskite type materials have been proven having a high hydrogen storage capacity, therefore perovskite is currently extensively studied also due to hydrogen storage [21,22]. We remind the reader that hydrogen is the most common element in the universe with a large energy density, non-toxic, carbon free and easy to be produced [23–25]. Note, that the storage and transportation of hydrogen remain challenging, and researchers have been diligently working on the development of novel materials for hydrogen storage [26,27]. It can be stored in either liquid state through liquefaction or gaseous states via gas compression [28–30]. The gravimetric density and hydrogen desorption temperature are two important performance indicators for evaluating hydrogen storage materials [31,32]. Higher gravimetric density means more hydrogen can be stored in a smaller volume or mass of the storage material [33,34]. Hydrogen desorption temperature refers to the temperature at which hydrogen molecules are released from a solid storage material [35]. To achieve controlled release of hydrogen, maintaining a moderate hydrogen desorption temperature is crucial. Hence, the advancement of hydrogen storage materials possessing high gravimetric density along with moderate hydrogen desorption temperatures is the key for enhancing the storage and utilization of hydrogen energy [32,36,37].

During past decades, the field of perovskite materials is growing exponentially in terms of both the published papers and research groups being involved. The purpose of this review is to provide the overview of the recent findings and trends in perovskite used in photovoltaic and hydrogen storage. Our review would, therefore, help researchers to keep up with current achievements, challenges and future directions in this growing field of the perovskite materials.

2. Perovskite materials used in photovoltaic

2.1. Perovskite solar cells

A variety of perovskite compounds are available in different forms, including carbides, nitrides, fluorides, chlorides, bromides, oxides, hydrides and iodides [38,39]. Among them oxides and hydrides are the predominant structural configurations with potential applicability for hydrogen storage [40–43]. The standard formula for perovskite compounds is ABX_3 , wherein both A and B represent cations, and X denote an anion, see Figure 1 [44–46]. When hydrogen, oxygen, halide atom, nitrogen or fluorine replaces element X within a compound, the resulting entities are known as perovskite hydride, perovskite oxide, perovskite halide, perovskite nitride and perovskite fluoride, respectively [47–51].

Figure 1. Crystal structure of hybrid organic-inorganic perovskite materials.

The PSCs are mostly based on hybrid organic-inorganic compounds with the formula ABX_3 structure, where A is a cation such as cesium, methylammonium(MA), and/or formamidinium (FA); B is a divalent metal cation such as lead or tin; and X is a halide

such as iodide, bromide and/or chloride, see Figure 1 [52,53]. In general, the PSCs consist of five fundamental layers: the perovskite light-absorber layer, the transparent conductive oxide as a conducting substrate (typically tin-doped indium oxide or fluorine-doped tin oxide), the metal (mainly gold, silver or copper), and two charge transport layers, typically the electron transport layer and the hole transport layer [54]. PSCs have a similar operating principle as conventional heterojunction or p-i-n solar cells. The light absorbed by the perovskite absorber layer produces free electron-hole pairs (excitons are weakly bound), which are subsequently transported to the charge transport layer interfaces, producing an open-circuit voltage and a photocurrent [55–57]. Restricting the analysis to the function of the hole transport material in optimizing PCE, its highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energy levels must be strategically aligned with those of the perovskite and the back electrode within the device. With vacuum level as the reference, the HOMO level of hole transport materials should be higher in energy than the perovskite valence band in order to facilitate hole transportation from the perovskite. Secondly, the LUMO of the hole transport materials should be as high as possible with respect to the perovskite conduction band as also depicted in Fig. 1 [58]. The latter conduction band offset would avoid electrons traveling from the perovskite to the hole transport materials and, as a result, reducing the current and voltage due to the recombination with holes in the hole transporting layer or at the interfaces. Furthermore, the HOMO level of the hole transport materials should be positioned just below the Fermi level of the back electrode to ensure rapid charge collection [55,59,60].

Generally, PSC devices are typically divided into two types based on their planar architecture: conventional (n-i-p) PSCs and inverted (p-i-n) PSCs. (see Fig. 2) [61]. Many recent studies on the high-performance conventional PSCs utilizes tin oxide (SnO_2) or spiro-OMeTAD, whereas for a high-performance p-i-n devices the PTAA or self-assembled molecules, and PC_{61}BM or C_{60} are primarily used [62–67]. It is important to note that an alternative strategy of PSCs fabrication which enables to achieve an extraordinarily high certified power conversion efficiency of $\sim 25.8\%$ has only recently being reported by Zhou et al [68]. This strategy utilizes the modulation of anion- π interaction with halide in the AX component. As a result, it helps to establish the so-called dual-site regulation and, correspondingly, it improves a phase and component purity at nanoscale [69].

Figure 2. Band diagram and main process and PSC: (1) Absorption of photon and free charges generation; (2) Charge transport; (3) Charge extraction. Here HTL stands for hole transport layer; FTO for fluorine-doped tin oxide and ETL is electron transport layer. Results are reproduced from [58] with permission from Elsevier.

Figure 3. Four device configurations of PSCs: mesoscopic structure, planar structure, triple mesoscopic structure, and tandem structure with lower-bandgap subcell. Here TCO is the transparent conductive oxide and ETL is electron transport layer. Present results are reproduced from [61] with permission from AAAS

2.1. Other solar cells systems utilizing properties of perovskite materials

First of all, we remind the reader that the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of a single junction solar cell is limited by ratio of the bandgap of the absorber over the elementary charge. Hence, in a single junction cell, an absorber with a narrower bandgap is unable to generate a high V_{oc} due to limitations imposed by its bandgap. Conversely, an absorber with a wider bandgap has the potential to yield a higher V_{oc} ; however, the short-circuit current is restricted because photons with energy lower than the absorber's bandgap do not contribute to the photocurrent. The limited efficiency of these solar cells (i.e., one p-n junction) can also be overcome by combining more cells together with different bandgap energy (i.e., two / multiple p-n junctions) and they are known as tandem / triple etc. solar cells [70,71].

These tandem solar cells usually consist of two types of solar cells: perovskite-silicon (or perovskite - CIGS) and all-perovskite solar cells. In this case, the top layer is usually made of a wide-bandgap perovskite material that absorbs high-energy photons, while the bottom layer consists of a narrow-bandgap material like silicon or copper indium gallium diselenide (CIGS) that absorbs lower-energy photons (see Fig. 3) [61,72,73]. For instance, *Tockhorn et al.* [74] has fabricated perovskite-silicon tandem solar cells with periodic nanostructures that reduced the reflection losses compare to planar tandems and increased fabrication yield from 50% to 95%. Moreover, the enhanced optoelectronic properties of the perovskite top cell resulted in a significant improvement in V_{oc} by 15 mV. Finally, they have reported a certified power conversion efficiency of 29.8% [75]. Surprisingly, all-perovskite tandem solar cells with an efficiency of 20.7% has been also demonstrated [76,77]. In this case, chlorine has been incorporated to increase crystallinity and carrier mobility, reduce electronic disorder and suppress trap-assisted recombination in low- E_g perovskite grains, and, as a result, enhance a performance in devices utilizing thick absorber layers.

Perovskite materials are also employed in flexible, semitransparent or space solar cells. In the case of flexible PSCs, the perovskite is fabricated on the flexible substrate such as poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) using thermal radiation annealing [78]. It has shown that a high power conversion efficiency of ~22.61% and a remarkable fill factor of 83.42% can be achieved by means of dual-sided annealing [79]. Briefly, dual side annealing allows to remain the PET undistorted during high-temperature annealing, and to reduce the grain boundaries, decrease lattice mismatch, and achieve cleaner vertical stacking of grains in perovskite.

Semitransparent solar cells are used in building windows and/or cladding, and vehicle integration. The transparency of perovskite solar cells relies on both the bandgap of the perovskite layer and the transmittance of the electrode. A thin metal layer frequently serves as the transparent electrode in semitransparent solar cells. For instance, Ju et al. reported a semitransparent PSC with a 3D-structured fluorine-doped tin oxide enhanced the diffuse transmittance and shortened the carrier travel distance. They have reported that transparent PSC devices achieved a power conversion efficiency between 12.0% and 14.6%, and an average visible transmittance of 13.4-17.0% [80].

Solar cells face numerous challenges in the space environment, particularly from cosmic radiation. PSCs have demonstrated impressive resilience against different types of radiation, including electrons, protons, ultraviolet rays, and gamma rays [81–83]. The effect of high doses of 1 MeV e-beam radiation up to an accumulated fluence to 10^{16} e \cdot cm $^{-2}$ on perovskite thin films and solar cells have been reported by *Pérez-del-Rey* et al. [84]. They found that PSCs based on quartz substrates remain stable even under high doses of 1 MeV e-beam irradiation. Analysis of time-resolved microwave conductivity in both pristine and irradiated films revealed a slight decrease in the charge carrier diffusion length following irradiation.

3. Perovskite-type hydrogen storage - overview

In the case of hydrogen storage it is necessary that materials can fulfill the following conditions: 1) the hydrogen bonds in these materials are of remarkable strength; 2) these materials encompass a substantial volume, facilitating the storage of a significant amount of hydrogen; 3) these materials exhibit catalytic properties that enhance hydrogen uptake; and, 4) also exhibit acceptable gravimetric hydrogen storage capabilities, contributing to enhanced hydrogen storage capacity [85,86]. The perovskite for hydrogen storage utilizes hydride, oxide and halide ones.

3.1. Perovskite-type Hydride

The compounds formulated as ABH₃ referred to as perovskite-type hydrides are having stable structures and distinctive properties; therefore, they have gained a considerable attention from the scientific community [87,88]. The perovskite hydrides are usually categorized into two groups, based on the selected elements A and B in the perovskite structure. In the first group, the element A and B could be selected from group I and II of the periodic table. [89]. Typical members of this structure group are BaLiH₃, CsCaH₃, KMgH₃, NaMgH₃, RbCaH₃ or SrLiH₃. Among different types of ABH₃, the magnesium-based perovskite hydrides have recently received a particular attention from researchers due to a high hydrogen storage capacity. For example, the superior gravimetric and volumetric hydrogen storage densities of 6% and 88 kg/m³ of NaMgH₃ has already been demonstrated [30]. The second group consists of those of perovskite-type hydrides, where element A is either a monovalent alkali metal or a divalent metal, and element B is a transition metal. Some examples of the compounds of this structural group include CaCoH₃, CaNiH₃, LiTH₃ (T: Fe, Co, Ni, Cu), SrPdH₃, and SrLiH₃.

3.2. Perovskite-type Oxides

The formula of typically perovskite-type oxides is composed of ABO₃, the ABO₃ perovskite-type oxides possesses not only a remarkable hydrogen storage capacity, but also long-term stability [90,91]. Nowadays, the perovskite-type oxides have emerged as suitable materials for efficient electrocatalysis in hydrogen conversion and storage, owing to their distinctive physical and chemical attributes, that is, a superior redox activity, flexible structure, remarkable ionic/electronic conductivity, and outstanding thermal and chemical stability [92,93]. Researchers are devoted to study the performance of perovskite-type oxides for hydrogen storage at a room temperature [94]. The pioneer study of Sakaguchi et al. [95] has revealed that perovskites (SrCe_{0.95}Yb_{0.05}O₃) can store hydrogen at even a room

temperature in the context of Ni/MH systems. A few years later, the maximum hydrogen absorption capacity of $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_3$ was determined to be 1.72 wt% at 333 K and 6 mol-L⁻¹ KOH, as recalculated from the electrochemical capacity [96].

3.3. Halide-type perovskite

The metal halide perovskites as absorbent materials have also great potential to become the next generation of energy storage devices [97,98]. Although the metal halide perovskites exhibit excellent performance, the environmentally harmful elements, such as lead (Pb) are the drawbacks limiting their application potential [99,100]. Thus, scientists are trying to replace these harmful elements with non-toxic metals in the perovskite structure [101,102]. For example, tin has been used to replace lead in calcium titanium perovskite solar cells and, as such, develop the lead-free halide perovskite materials [103,104]. Another area of research involves studying the elemental contributions towards the band structure of S-block perovskites, which exhibit similarities to Pb-perovskites [105]. Building on previous efforts, Adeyinka et al. [106] utilized density functional theory calculations to determine the hydrogen storage capacities of KBeH_3 , KMgH_3 , and KCaH_3 , which were found to be 5.866%, 4.516%, and 3.649%, respectively.

Figure 4. The crystal structure of MgXH_3 for $X = \text{Co}$, $X = \text{Cu}$, $X = \text{Ni}$.

4. Perovskite-type hydrides structural, thermodynamic, and hydrogen storage properties

The fundamental properties of perovskite-type hydrides are routinely obtained from the first-principles calculations using the density-functional theory (DFT). In this section, we will present the recent data on the properties of the currently considered perovskite-hydrides materials, that is, Mg-based perovskite-type hydrides MgXH_3 ($X = \text{Co}$, Cu , Ni) [107], Ca-based perovskite-type hydrides CaXH_3 ($X = \text{Mn}$, Fe , Co) [39], and metal base perovskite-hydrides AeSiH_3 ($\text{Ae} = \text{K}$, Li , Na , Mg) [108], AeVH_3 ($\text{Ae} = \text{Be}$, Mg , Ca , Sr) [109], XSrH_3 ($X = \text{K}$ and Rb) [29], XCuH_3 ($X = \text{Co}$, Ni , Zn) [110], XCoH_3 ($X = \text{In}$, Mn , Sr , Sn , Cd) [111], XPtH_3 ($X = \text{Li}$, Na , K , Rb) [112], XAlH_3 ($X = \text{Na}$, K) [113] and XTiH_3 ($X = \text{K}$, Rb , Cs) [32].

The calculated structure of MgXH_3 ($X = \text{Co}$, Cu , Ni) hydride perovskite is given in Fig. 4. In the unit cell, the Mg atoms are located at the corners with coordinates, the metal atoms X- is in the center of the unit cell with coordinates, and the H atoms are at the octahedral sites at the center of faces. The assessment of the stability of materials MgCoH_3 , MgCuH_3 , and MgNiH_3 have been determined utilizing the *Birch-Murnaghan* equation of state in conjugation with energy volume cures [114,115]. Mathematically, it can be obtained from

$$E_{total}(V) = E_0(V) + \frac{B_0 V}{B'_0(-1)} \left[B_0 \left(1 - \frac{V_0}{V} \right) + \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right)^{B'_0} - 1 \right], \quad (1)$$

where $E_0(V)$ is the total energy of the ground state of a unite cell at a given volume V , V_0 is the equilibrium volume, B_0 is the bulk modulus and B'_0 stands its derivate with respect to pressure. Then, the gravimetric storage capacity of hydride perovskite which is of importance in hydrogen storage applications, is estimated from the gravimetric ratio [116]

$$Cwt [\%] = \left(\frac{\frac{A_H}{A_M} m_H}{m_M + \frac{A_H}{A_M} m_H} \times 100 \right) [\%]. \quad (2)$$

Here m and A stand for the molar mass and atoms, respectively; and subscript H stands for hydrogen and subscript M means the host perovskite material. Theoretically achievable amounts of hydrogen stored per unit mass of the host perovskite for all three Mg-based perovskites (i.e., Co, Cu, Ni) are summarized in Table 1. Note that the hydrogen desorption temperature (T_{des}), which is an essential parameter for assessing the temperature required to release the stored hydrogen can be determined from

$$T_{des} = \frac{\Delta H}{\Delta S}, \quad (3)$$

where ΔH and ΔS are the formation energy and entropy change of hydrogen ($130.7 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), respectively.

Table 1. The calculated lattice constant ($a = b = c$ in Å), volume (V in Å³), density (ρ in g/cm³), formation enthalpy (ΔH in kJ/mol•H₂), gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity (Cwt% in wt%), and desorption temperature (T_{des} in K) for MgXH₃, where X = Co, Cu, Ni, respectively [107].

Compounds	Cwt%	a_0 (Å)	V (Å ³)	ρ (g/cm ³)	ΔH_f (eV/atom)	T_{des} (K)
MgCoH ₃	3.64	3.32	36.44	3.93	- 70.93	542.69
MgCuH ₃	3.32	3.49	42.42	3.56	- 63.27	484.08
MgNiH ₃	3.49	3.36	37.97	3.76	- 68.54	524.40

The structure of CaXH₃ is similar to the above discussed perovskite-type hydride (i.e., in the present case Mg is just replaced by Ca in Fig. 3). The fundamental properties of the CaXH₃ are given in Table 2. After calculation, the lattice constant (Å), volume (V in Å³), density (ρ in g/cm³), formation enthalpies (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity (Cwt% in wt%) of the hydrides studied are given in Table 2. The negative values of the formation enthalpies listed in Table 2 indicate that CaXH₃ (X: Mn, Fe, Co) perovskite-type hydrides are thermodynamically stable and can be synthesized. Among them, CaCoH₃ has the highest stability, which is given by

$$\Delta H_f = E_t(\text{CaXH}_3) - [E(\text{Ca}) + E(\text{X}) + 3 \times E(\text{H})], \quad (4)$$

where $E_t(\text{CaXH}_3)$ symbolize total energy of CaXH₃ and $E(\text{Ca})$, $E(\text{X})$, and $E(\text{H})$ are the ground state energies for one Ca atom, one X atom, and one H atom, respectively [39].

Table 2. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), volumes (V), densities (ρ), formation enthalpies (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities (Cwt%) of CaXH₃ (X: Mn, Fe, or Co) compounds [39].

Compounds	Cwt%	a_0 (Å)	V (Å ³)	ρ (g/cm ³)	ΔH_f (eV/atom)
CaMnH ₃	3.09	3.60	46.58	3.50	- 0.25
CaFeH ₃	3.06	3.50	42.99	3.82	- 0.42
CaCoH ₃	2.97	3.48	42.16	4.03	- 0.44

Figure 5. The crystal structures of AeSiH_3 for $\text{Ae} = \text{K}$, $\text{Ae} = \text{Li}$, $\text{Ae} = \text{Na}$, $\text{Ae} = \text{Mg}$.

The crystal structure of cubic AeSiH_3 ($\text{Ae} = \text{K}$, Li , Na , Mg) compounds is shown in Fig. 5. In the unit cell, the atoms Ae-are at the corners with coordinates, the Si atoms are located in the center of the unit cell with coordinates, and the H atoms are at the octahedral sites at the center of faces. The formation enthalpies of AeSiH_3 hydrides are estimated as follow [108]:

$$\Delta H_f (\text{AeSiH}_3) = [E_t(\text{AeSiH}_3) - [E_s(\text{Ae}) + E_s(\text{Si}) - 3E_s(\text{H})]] \quad (5)$$

where $E_s(\text{Ae})$ shows the energy of Ae ($\text{Ae} = \text{Li}$, K , Na , Mg) atoms, $E_s(\text{Si})$ shows the energy of Si atoms, and $E_s(\text{H})$ shows the ground state energy of H atoms. E_t shows the total energy of the compound. After calculation, the lattice constant (\AA), volume (V in \AA^3), density (ρ in g/cm^3), formation energy (ΔH_f in eV/atom), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity (Cwt% in wt%) of the hydrides studied are summarized in Table 3. We emphasize here that the higher entropy values contribute to the release of hydrogen from perovskite materials. Perovskite materials with lower hydrogen adsorption free energy values have a higher affinity for hydrogen gas, making them more likely to store hydrogen efficiently.

Table 3. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), volumes (V), densities (ρ), formation energy (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities (Cwt%) of AeSiH_3 ($\text{Ae} = \text{Li}$, K , Na , Mg) compounds [108].

Compounds	Cwt%	$a_0(\text{\AA})$	$V(\text{\AA}^3)$	$\rho(\text{g/cm}^3)$	$\Delta H_f(\text{eV/atom})$
LiSiH_3	7.946	4.001	64.079	1.046	- 17.372
KSiH_3	4.306	3.917	60.122	1.952	- 15.760
NaSiH_3	5.588	3.986	63.363	1.429	- 16.134
MgSiH_3	5.456	3.977	62.933	1.476	- 15.063

We only note that structure of AeVH_3 , where $\text{Ae} = \text{Be}$, Mg , Ca , and Sr , is similar to the perovskite-type hydride presented in Fig. 5. [109]. The lattice parameters(\AA) are calculated as 3.48, 3.66, 3.73 and 3.83; The volumes (\AA^3) are calculated as 42.21, 49.22, 53.28 and 56.22 respectively for AeVH_3 with $\text{Ae} = \text{Be}$, Mg , Ca , and Sr . For the perovskite hydrides AeVH_3 (where $\text{Ae} = \text{Be}$, Mg , Ca , Sr), the gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity decreases with increasing alkaline metal (Ae) mass, with values of 4.6, 3.7, 3.1 and 2.0 wt%, respectively. This trend shows that the decreasing gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity is due to the increasing mass of alkaline metals. Consequently, BeVH_3 stands out as the most suitable material for hydrogen storage applications, with a higher gravimetric density of 4.6 wt% compared to the other three materials studied [109].

The following are perovskite-type hybrids with identical structures but with different atomic arrangements. A brief description of their structures is given below, followed by the calculated values. All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of XSrH_3 ($X = \text{K}$ and Rb) are given in Table 4. KSrH_3 has a greater capacity to store hydrogen (2.33%) compared to RbSrH_3 (1.71%). In the context of illustrating thermodynamic properties, The Debye temperature is a crucial parameter in the discussion of the quasiharmonic Debye

model and various thermodynamic properties. As the temperature increases, the Debye temperature decreases. Similarly, the Debye temperature increases at higher pressures. KSrH₃ has a higher Debye temperature value compared to RbSrH₃. It can therefore be said that KSrH₃ is more stable than RbSrH₃ [29].

Table 4. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), volumes (V), formation energy (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities (Cwt%) of XSrH₃ ($X = K$ and Rb) compounds [29].

Compounds	Cwt%	a_0 (Å)	V (Å ³)	ΔH_f (eV/atom)
KSrH ₃	2.33	4.77	108.50	- 6.60
RbSrH ₃	1.71	4.99	124.77	- 5.67

All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of XCuH₃ ($X = Co, Ni, Zn$) are given in Table 5. NiCuH₃ has a greater capacity to store hydrogen (3.0%) compared to CoCuH₃ (2.8%) and ZnCuH₃ (2.7%). In the thermodynamic properties, the negative values of free energy deliberate the thermodynamic stability of any material, the free energy of these three materials is all negative, indicating that they are stable materials in relation to each other. CoCuH₃ is more stable than NiCuH₃ and ZnCuH₃ because CoCuH₃ has the lowest free energy of them [110].

Table 5. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), volumes (V), free energy (F), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities (Cwt%) of XCuH₃ ($X = Co, Ni, Zn$) compounds [110].

Compounds	Cwt%	a_0 (Å)	V (Å ³)	ΔH_f (eV/atom)
CoCuH ₃	2.8	3.3287	36.882	- 1895.3
NiCuH ₃	3.0	3.3245	36.742	- 5499.0
ZnCuH ₃	2.7	3.6129	47.160	- 2512.5

All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of XCoH₃ ($X = In, Mn, Sr, Sn, Cd$) are given in Table 6. MnCoH₃ is most favored for hydrogen storage properties because its gravimetric ratio for hydrogen storage is greater than all these studied materials [111].

Table 6. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), volumes (V), formation energy (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities (Cwt%) of XCoH₃ ($X = In, Mn, Sr, Sn, Cd$) compounds [111].

Compounds	Cwt%	a_0 (Å)	V (Å ³)	ΔH_f (eV/atom)
CdCoH ₃	1.74	3.42	20.00	- 0.93
InCoH ₃	1.71	3.52	43.61	- 1.09
MnCoH ₃	2.59	3.60	46.66	- 0.87
SnCoH ₃	1.68	3.59	46.27	- 1.31
SrCoH ₃	2.03	3.66	49.03	- 0.78

All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of XPtH₃ ($X = Li, Na, K, Rb$) are given in Table 7. Compared to other materials, LiPtH₃ exhibits the highest gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities and stability (T_{des}) [112].

Table 7. The calculated lattice constant (a_0), volume (V), formation energy (ΔH_f), gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity (Cwt%), and desorption temperature (T_{des}) for XPtH₃ ($X = Li, Na, K, Rb$) [112].

Compounds	Cwt%	a_0 (Å)	V (Å ³)	ΔH_f (eV/atom)	T_{des} (K)
LiPtH ₃	1.45	3.54	44.35	- 0.32	237.77
NaPtH ₃	1.35	3.63	47.96	- 0.31	225.39
KPtH ₃	1.26	3.80	54.83	- 0.22	162.43
RbPtH ₃	1.06	3.90	59.25	- 0.11	80.11

All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of XAlH₃ ($X = Na, K$) are given in Table 8. NaAlH₃ has a higher gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity than KAlH₃. The

formation energies of these compounds are negative, demonstrating their thermodynamic stability [113].

Table 8. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), volumes (V), formation energy (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities ($C_{wt\%}$) of $XAlH_3$ ($X = Na, K$) compounds [113].

Compounds	$C_{wt\%}$	$a_0(\text{\AA})$	$V(\text{\AA}^3)$	$\Delta H_f(\text{eV/atom})$
NaAlH ₃	5.40	3.792	54.526	- 0.903
KAlH ₃	4.19	3.938	61.070	- 1.250

All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of $XTiH_3$ ($X = K, Rb, Cs$) are given in Table 9. The weight hydrogen storage capacities of $KTiH_3$, $RbTiH_3$ and $CsTiH_3$ were determined to be 3.36, 2.22 and 1.65 wt%, respectively. The hydrogen desorption temperatures for $KTiH_3$, $RbTiH_3$ and $CsTiH_3$ were determined to be 209K, 161K and 107K, respectively. These results indicate that $KTiH_3$ has potential as a hydrogen storage material [32].

Table 9. The optimized lattice constants (a_0), bulk modulus B_0 (GPa), the derivative of bulk modulus B_0' (GPa), formation energy (ΔH_f), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities ($C_{wt\%}$) of $XTiH_3$ ($X = K, Rb, Cs$) compounds [32].

Compounds	$C_{wt\%}$	$a_0(\text{\AA})$	$B_0(\text{GPa})$	$B_0'(\text{GPa})$	$\Delta H_f(\text{eV/atom})$
$KTiH_3$	3.36	3.999	44.938	1.767	- 0.285
$RbTiH_3$	2.22	4.103	42.083	1.887	- 0.220
$CsTiH_3$	1.65	4.233	37.176	1.704	- 0.146

5. Perovskite-type oxides structural, thermodynamic, and hydrogen storage properties

Ostadebrahim et. al used a single-phase sol-gel method to synthesize ternary metal perovskite-type oxides $LaMO_3$ ($M = Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni$) and investigated their surface area, pore size, and electrochemical properties. The nanostructured materials parameters of the surface area and the pore size are crucial reference indicators for the electrochemical storage of hydrogen. According to the analysis results of BET-BJH, the BET surface area (S_{BET}), total pore volume (V_t), average pore diameter (D_{avg}) and SBJH of the samples are shown in Table 10. In the electrochemical performance of $LaMO_3$ in a three-electrode electrochemical cell, $LaFeO_3$ achieved the highest current density at the anodic peak. As shown in Table 10, $LaFeO_3$ exhibited a morphology characterised by a spherical shape, the maximum number of nanoparticles per unit area, the highest total pore volume (V_t) and the lowest average pore diameter (D_{avg}). This morphology is indicative of superior electrode response [92].

Table 10. BET and BJH data of $LaMO_3$ ($M = Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni$) nanocrystals [92].

Samples	$S_{BET}(\text{m}^2/\text{g})$	$V_t(\text{cm}^3/\text{g})$	$D_{avg}(\text{nm})$	$S_{BJH}(\text{m}^2/\text{g})$
LaCrO ₃	1.4838	0.0044	12.060	5.8201
LaMnO ₃	8.8778	0.0302	13.616	6.7078
LaFeO ₃	20.997	0.1201	10.721	20.698
LaCoO ₃	8.2064	0.0693	33.807	10.929
LaNiO ₃	4.8519	0.0562	98.998	16.537

The electrochemical hydrogen storage capacity of $LaMO_3$ nanocrystals is shown in Table 11. $LaFeO_3$ shows the most favorable performance in terms of electrochemical hydrogen storage capacity. The lifetime and stability of the electrochemical hydrogen storage was investigated by galvanostatic charge-discharge tests and Tafel polarisation analysis. The $LaFeO_3$ electrode exhibited stable discharge capacity over a current range of 1 to 4 mA. The Tafel test results showed the lowest corrosion rate for $LaFeO_3$ nano-perovskites. These results shows that $LaFeO_3$ nano-perovskites is a promising candidate for energy storage applications [92].

Table 11. Electrochemical hydrogen storage capacity of LaMO₃ (M= Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni) nanocrystals [92].

Active material	Substrate	Electrolyte solution	Reference electrode	Counter electrode	Discharge capacity
LaCrO ₃					6790 mAh/g
LaMnO ₃					10500 mAh/g
LaFeO ₃	Cu electrode	6M KOH	Ag/AGCl	Pt	13500 mAh/g
LaCoO ₃					8800 mAh/g
LaNiO ₃					7000 mAh/g

Bhardwaj et. al used perovskite oxide materials, specifically the proton insertion anode Sm_{1-x}Sr_xCoO_{3-δ} (x = 0, 0.5, 1) for nickel/oxide rechargeable batteries. Sm_{1-x}Sr_xCoO_{3-δ} (x = 0, 0.5, 1) was synthesised via solid state reactions and its electrochemical hydrogen storage performance in alkaline electrolytes. The oxygen-deficient Sm_{0.5}Sr_{0.5}CoO_{3-δ} (SSC) exhibits a maximum reversible discharge capacity of 182 mAh g⁻¹, which increases with increasing temperature. Partial substitution of the acceptor dopant strontium with samarium induces lattice expansion, a greater extent of Co-O interactions and increases the reducibility of cobalt ions, thereby promoting higher hydrogen storage [117].

Nabil et. al studied the electronic, mechanical and elastic properties of LaCrO₃H_x (x = 0, 6) for hydrogen storage applications have been investigated. The determination included cell parameters, crystal structure and mechanical performance. In terms of electronic properties, the Fermi level density of states (DOS) for LaCrO₃ and LaCrO₃H₆ is exceptionally low. This indicates that the lower the DOS of the Fermi level, the more stable the compound. Table 12 shows that LaCrO₃ has a higher bulk modulus value and when hydrogen binds to LaCrO₃ the bulk modulus decreases, indicating greater material compressibility. In conclusion, the LaCrO₃ compound has a remarkable hydrogen storage capacity of about 4 wt% [118].

Table 12. Cell parameters, mechanical properties of LaCrO₃ and LaCrO₃H₆ [118].

Compounds	Calculated cell parameters (Å)	B ₀ (GPa)	B ₀ ' (GPa)
LaCrO ₃	3.85	128.07	3.2
LaCrO ₃ H ₆	4.43	62.26	23.48

All calculated gravimetric hydrogen storage capacities of perovskite-type hydrides/oxide KMO_{3-x}H_x (x = 0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9, 1.2, 1.5, 1.8, 2.1, 2.4, 2.7, and 3.0) are given in Table 13. MnCoH₃ is most favored for hydrogen storage properties because its gravimetric ratio for hydrogen storage is greater than all these studied materials. The calculated lattice parameters indicate that KMg has a cubic crystal structure in KMgO₃ and KMgH₃. However, for other doping concentrations, the cubic crystal structure is distorted when anions are doped on the anion side [119].

Table 13. The calculated lattice constant (a = b = c in Å), volume (V in Å³), formation enthalpy (ΔH in kJ/mol•H₂), gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity (Cwt% in wt%), and desorption temperature (T_{des} in K) for KMO_{3-x}H_x (x = 0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9, 1.2, 1.5, 1.8, 2.1, 2.4, 2.7, and 3.0) [119].

Compounds	Cwt%	a ₀ (Å)			V (Å ³)	ΔH _f (eV/atom)	T _{des} (K)
		a	b	c			
KMgO ₃	-	4.109	-	-	69.37	- 0.023	-
KMg _{2.7} O _{0.3}	0.28	4.102	4.102	4.112	69.19	- 11.122	825
KMg _{2.4} O _{0.6}	0.59	4.092	4.067	4.140	68.90	- 10.826	803
KMg _{2.1} O _{0.9}	0.92	4.059	4.057	4.162	68.54	- 10.529	781
KMg _{1.8} O _{1.2}	1.28	4.034	4.038	4.196	68.35	- 10.223	759
KMg _{1.5} O _{1.5}	1.67	4.107	3.989	4.182	68.51	- 9.937	737
KMg _{1.2} O _{1.8}	2.10	4.510	4.653	4.437	92.90	- 9.648	716

KMg _{0.9} O _{2.1}	2.58	4.450	3.975	4.108	72.60	- 9.347	694
KMg _{0.6} O _{2.4}	3.10	4.156	3.966	4.091	67.43	- 8.624	640
KMg _{0.3} O _{2.7}	3.69	4.058	4.084	4.004	66.35	- 7.904	587
KMgH ₃	4.35	4.069	-	-	67.36	- 7.606	564

6. Halide perovskite structural, thermodynamic, and hydrogen storage properties

Mbonu et. al used DFT to calculate the structural properties of the S-block halide perovskite $KXCl_3$ ($X = Be, Ca, Mg$). In terms of thermodynamic performance, $KMgCl_3$ has the highest heat capacity, while $KCaCl_3$ has the lowest. In order to investigate the hydrogen storage capabilities of this perovskite system, functionalization was carried out by replacing chlorine (Cl) atoms in the crystal lattice with hydrogen (H) atoms. The resulting functionalised compounds, $KBeH_3$, $KMgH_3$ and $KCaH_3$ are detailed in Table 14. $KBeH_3$ has the best gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity of 5.866%, surpassing $KMgH_3$ and $KCaH_3$ [120].

Table14. The calculated lattice constant ($a=b=c$ in Å), volume (V in Å³), bulk modulus B_0 (GPa), formation enthalpy (ΔH in kJ/mol•H₂), and gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity ($Cwt\%$ in wt%) for KXH_3 ($X = Be, Ca, Mg$) [120].

Compounds	$Cwt\%$	$a_0(\text{Å})$	$V(\text{Å}^3)$	$B_0(\text{GPa})$	$\Delta H_f(\text{eV/atom})$
KBeH ₃	5.866	4.41	158.385	2.650	- 1.226
KMgH ₃	4.516	4.74	297.538	0.916	- 2.523
KCaH ₃	3.649	5.10	89.719	27.902	- 1.845

7. Conclusion remarks

In this review, we have presented not only the applications of perovskite solar cells but also the hydrogen storage capacities of perovskite-type materials. Due to their excellent structural properties and cost-effectiveness, perovskite materials offer substantial research potential in the field of hydrogen storage.

The main future advancements for perovskite solar cells include the development of tandem solar cells, flexible solar cells, and space solar cells. Among perovskite-type hydrides, $LiSiH_3$ exhibits the highest gravimetric hydrogen storage capacity at 7.946%, highlighting the significant potential of this compound series for hydrogen storage. Additionally, perovskite-type oxides demonstrate excellent hydrogen adsorption and storage capabilities in electrode applications, leading to increased electrode capacity and robust cycling stability. The low application cost of these materials in energy storage systems further emphasizes the development potential of perovskite-type oxides for hydrogen storage.

These findings collectively underscore the promising prospects of perovskite-type hydrides and oxides in the field of hydrogen storage. Overall, the present results are highly significant for future research on perovskite-type hydrogen storage compounds and the development of perovskite solar cells.

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